

EFFECT OF NEEM CAKE FOR CONTROL OF OROBANCHE IN MUSTARD CROP FOR HIGHER YIELD AND INCOME IN JAIPUR DISTRICT OF RAJASTHAN

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Abstract

Mustard is grown as cash crop in Jaipur district and farmers are getting good price after harvest but due to the infestation of orobanche the yield reduced up to 30 % (as discussed with farming community).

Orobanche, a super sink to mustard crop has threatened the farming community to rethink for alternative option as this parasitic weed has become a menace to Indian mustard [*Brassica juncea* (L.) Czern & Coss.] cultivation in India. The germinating seed (host dependent seed conditioning and stimulation) produces a germ tube or radical which elongates chemotropically and forms a haustorium that is strongly attached to the plant vascular system (Dorr and Kollmann, 1976; Parker and Riches, 1993). The attached parasite functions as a strong metabolic sink, often named "super-sink", strongly efficiently competing with the host plant for water and mineral nutrition causing moisture and assimilates starvation, host plant stress and growth inhibition leading to significant reduction in crop yield and distressed crop quality in infested fields. Depending upon the extent of infestation, environmental factors, soil fertility, and the crop competitiveness, damage from Orobanche can range from zero to complete crop failure (Dhanapal et al., 1996). Some of the farmers even abandoned the cultivation of mustard under the threat of this parasitic weed. The present study was carried out at farmers field of Jaipur district of Rajasthan during Rabi 2018-19, 2019-20 and 2020-21, which falls in agro-climatic zone III a (Semi-arid eastern plain) of Rajasthan. The soils of experimental field was sandy loam in texture normal in reaction (pH 7.0 -8.5) low in organic matter (0.21-0.48) and available nitrogen (95 kg/ha-225kg/ha) low to medium available phosphorus (13 kg/ha-23kg/ha) and medium to high in available potassium (145 kg/ha-285kg/ha) the study consist two treatments i.e. T₁-Farmers practice (One hand weeding) and T₂- Recommended practice (Neem Cake @200 kg/ha at sowing) on the basis of three year mean data application of Neem Cake @200 kg/ha at sowing is quite effective in reducing the weed infestation and substantially increase mustard yield and net returns. The result shows higher yield attributes, yield and net income with recommended practice (Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time) than farmers practice (One hand weeding).

Key words- Mustard, Orobanche, Neem cake, Hand weeding

Introduction

Brassica juncea (L.) Czern & Coss. originated from *Brassica rapa* and *Brassica nigra*. It is third important oil seed crop in the world after soybean and palm oil. In India it is second important oilseed crop after groundnut. Mustard oil is used for human consumption for cooking purpose, hair oil, soap making and medicines. The seed is also used as a condiment in preparation of pickles and for flavoring curries and vegetables. The oil cake contains sinigrin that causes palatability problems due to bitter in taste and glucosinolate limits its use as protein (Prasad R. 2012). India covers an area 6.70 million ha and 9.12 million tonnes production with 1345 kg/ha productivity (Anonymous 2020). Reduction in mustard yield due to poor weed management ranges from 10-58% depending upon weed flora, stage, intensity and duration of crop weed competition. Among the other weeds of mustard orobanche is heavy feeder of assimilates in mustard. This becomes a major problem for mustard growing farmers of Jaipur district of Rajasthan. Germinating seed of orobanche produces a germ tube which elongates chemo tropically and forms a haustorium that is attached with host plant vascular system (Parker C and Riches C.R. 1993) Orobanche has been proved difficult due to its underground location, lack of photosynthesis, late appearance of orobanche shoot, closer association with host plant roots and complex mechanism of seed dispersal, germination and longevity (Cubero J. I. and Moreno M.T.1979) When orobanche shoot become visible on and above the ground surface, most of damage has already occurred and conventional method of weed control would often become futile. Considering the vital importance of mustard in present oilseed scenario and huge financial burden of oilseed import on national economy, the present study was carried out at farmer's field of Jaipur district of Rajasthan during Rabi 2018-19, 2019-20 and 2020-21. During survey it is observed that farmers are using only one hand weeding for control of weeds in mustard. This present study "Effect of Neem Cake for control of orobanche in mustard crop for higher yield and income in Jaipur district of Rajasthan" was undertaken with following specific objectives

1. To find out the number of branches, number of siliqua per plant and test weight by using Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time in mustard.

2. To find out the grain yield of mustard by using Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time in mustard.

3. To find the net return and B:C ratio with Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time in mustard.

4. To find the Orobanche control efficiency with Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time in mustard.

Materials and methods:-

The present study was carried out at farmers' fields of Jaipur district of Rajasthan during Rabi 2018-19, 2019-20 and 2020-2021 which falls in agro climatic zone III a (semi-arid eastern plain zone) which covers the Jaipur, Ajmer, Tonk and Dausa district of Rajasthan. The soils of experimental fields were sandy loam in texture, normal in reaction (pH 7.0 -8.5) low in organic matter (0.21-0.48) and available nitrogen (95 kg/ha-225 kg/ha) low to medium available phosphorus (13 kg/ha-23 kg/ha) and medium to high in available potassium (145 kg/ha-285kg/ha) the study consist two treatments i.e. T₁-Farmers practice (One hand weeding) and T₂- Recommended practice (Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time) These treatments were replicated ten times at farmers' fields during three years of study. Observations on weed infestation were taken at each location at 100-110 days after sowing in per square meter area, number of branches per plant and number of siliqua per plant were taken 110-120 days after sowing and test weight and grain yield were taken after threshing and winnowing the crop management practices from sowing to harvest were followed as per package of practices of the zone III a. In this study special emphasis done to proper seed rate (4.0 kg/ha) balance use of fertilizers (60 kg/ha nitrogen and 30 kg/ha P₂O₅), Use of gypsum @ 250 kg/ha prior to sowing, high yielding variety (DRMR IJ-31), seed treatment with fungicide (Mencozeb 2.5 g/kg seed) insecticides (Imidachloprid 600 FS @ 10 ml/kg seed), irrigation at critical stages and need based plant protection measures during all the three years of study. The cross-section of data on output of mustard crop and input used per hectare have been collected and used for further calculation of cost of cultivation, gross returns, net returns benefit cost ratio and grain yield of mustard. The benefit cost (B:C) ratio was calculated by dividing gross returns by cost of cultivation.

Result and discussion

The data presented in Table (1) indicate that the Population of Orobanche per m² area were lower with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time (4.85) which was remarkably low as compared to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice (12.48) during rabi 2018-19. The similar trends were also observed during rabi 2019-20 and 2020-21. On the basis of three years mean data regarding Orobanche density, Orobanche population was recorded with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time (5.04) which was notably low as compare to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice (15.18). It is self explanatory from the Table 1 that treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time reduced the Orobanche population substantially as compared to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice during all three years of the study. The Orobanche control efficiency with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time 62.89 ,64.61 and 74.19 during rabi 2018-19,2019-20 and 2020-21 respectively. On the basis of three years mean data regarding Orobanche control efficiency with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time was 67.32.

The data presented in Table (2) indicate that the number of branches per plant were higher with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time (18.50) which was remarkably high as compared to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice (15.60) during rabi 2018-19. The similar trends were also observed during rabi 2019-20 and 2020-21. On the basis of three years mean data regarding branches per plant, branches per plant were recorded with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time (18.45) which was notably higher as compare to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice (15.53). The similar trends were also observed regarding number of siliqua per plan and number of seeds per siliqua.

The data presented in Table(3) indicate that Test weight was higher with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time (4.80 gm) which was remarkably high as compared to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice (4.62 gm) during rabi 2018-19. The similar trends were also observed during rabi 2019-20 and 2020-21. On the basis of three years mean data regarding Test weight were recorded with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time (4.84 gm) which was notably higher as compare to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice (4.65 gm). The similar trends were also observed regarding number grain yield, The data presented in Table (3) indicate that grain yield was higher with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time (20.19 qt/ha) which was remarkably high as compared to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice (16.16 qt/ha) during rabi 2018-19. The similar trends were also observed during rabi 2019-20 and 2020-21 with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time 22.12 and 22.81 qt/ha respectively which were remarkable higher than treatment T₁ Farmers Practice 18.07 and

19.24 qt/ha during rabi 2019-20 and 2020-21 respectively On the basis of three years mean data regarding grain yield with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time was 21.71 qt/ha as compare to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice 17.82 qt/ha. The results indicated that the use of T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time increase 27.43 per cent in yield over T₁ Farmers Practice (hand weeding). The similar results also observed by Jat B.L. and Meena R. L. 2018

The data presented in Table (4) indicate that Net returns were higher with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time (Rs. 43868) which was remarkably high as compared to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice (Rs. 33942) during rabi 2018-19. The similar trends were also observed during rabi 2019-20 and 2020-21 which were Rs. 50948 and Rs. 98555 with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time respectively as compared to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice Rs. 41216 and 81970 during rabi 2019-20 and 2020-21 On the basis of three years mean data regarding Net returns were recorded with treatment T₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time (64457) which was notably higher as compare to treatment T₁ Farmers Practice (52376). The similar trends were also observed regarding B:C ratio.

Conclusion:

On the basis of three year mean data application of Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at the time of sowing is quite effective in reducing the weed infestation and substantially increase mustard yield attributes, yield and net returns . The result shows higher yield attributes, yield and net income with recommended practice (Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing) than farmers practice (One hand weeding).

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Fig: 1 Effect of Neem Cake for control of orobanche in mustard

Table [1] Effect of Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time on orobanche control and Orobanche control efficiency

Technology Option	No. of trials	Number of Orobanche M ²				Dry Weight of Orobanche M ²				Orobanche control efficiency			
		2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average
T ₁ Farmers Practice	10	12.48	16.70	16.36	15.18	25.71	33.74	35.20	31.55	-	-	-	-
T ₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha		4.85	5.94	4.34	5.04	9.54	11.94	9.04	10.17	62.89	64.61	74.19	67.23

Table [2] Effect of Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time on Number of Branches per plant and Number of siliqua per plant of mustard

Technology Option	No. of trials	Number of Branches per plant				Number of siliqua per plant				Number of seeds per siliqua			
		2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average
T ₁ Farmers Practice	10	15.60	15.80	15.20	15.53	271	275	285	277	16.72	16.24	16.10	16.35
T ₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha		18.50	18.96	17.90	18.45	321	326	335	327	17.10	16.90	16.80	16.93

Table [3] Effect of Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time on Test weight and Yield of mustard

Technology Option	No. of trials	Test weight				Yield (qt/ha)				Cost of cultivation			
		2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average
T ₁ Farmers Practice	10	4.62	4.68	4.64	4.65	16.16	18.07	19.24	17.82	25850	24740	23850	24813
T ₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha		4.80	4.78	4.84	4.81	20.19	22.12	22.81	21.71	30835	27790	26900	28508

Table [4] Effect of Neem Cake @200 kg/ha soil incorporation at sowing time on Net returns and B: C ratio of mustard

Technology Option	No. of trials	Gross returns				Net returns				B: C ratio			
		2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Average
T ₁ Farmers Practice	10	59792	65956	105820	77189	33942	41216	81970	52376	2.31	2.67	4.44	3.14
T ₂ Neem Cake @200 kg/ha		74703	80738	125455	93632	43868	50948	98555	64457	2.42	2.91	4.66	3.33